

Knowledge And Attitude of Pregnant Women Towards Adherence to Childhood Routine Immunization in Primary Health Centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT

Childhood routine immunization is an important public health intervention strategy that protects children from vaccine-preventable diseases including; Measles, poliomyelitis, diphtheria, pertussis, tuberculosis and so on. Pregnant women play an important role to ensure that their children complete their immunization appointment, as they are the primary decision-makers in the family. The purpose of the study aims to assess the knowledge and attitudes of pregnant women towards adherence to childhood routine immunization in primary health centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area, Imo State. A descriptive survey was conducted among 240 respondents out of a total population of 1,449 pregnant women attending antenatal care services, in 7 selected primary health centres from the 14 existing primary health centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area, using a multi stage sampling technique including; simple random sampling technique and proportionate stratified sampling technique. Two instruments were designed by the researcher viz; Knowledge Test on Childhood Routine Immunization (KTCRI) and Attitude Towards Adherence to Childhood Routine Immunization (ATACRI) questionnaire were used for data collection. The reliability of the instruments was determined using the Kuder-Richardson (K-R20) method for the knowledge test, which yielded a coefficient value of 0.97. Additionally, Cronbach's Alpha internal consistency measure for the attitude items yielded a coefficient value of 0.94. The statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 25, descriptive statistics such as frequency table, means, standard deviations and inferential statistics of one way analysis of variance (ANOVA), post hoc multiple comparison tests were used to present and analyze the data. The study findings, conclusion and recommendations were made respectively.

Introduction

Immunization is considered one of the world's most cost-effective public health interventions, preventing an estimated 4.4 million deaths each year and protecting millions of children from preventable illness and disability (United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), 2024). According to Okumu (2020), immunization is the process whereby the body's immune system is stimulated by a vaccine making the person immune or resistant to an infectious

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disease. Immunization and vaccination are common terms used interchangeably in the field of public health.

Vaccination is a simple, safe, and effective way to protect an individual against harmful diseases before they are exposed to them (World Health Organization, 2024). It involves the administration of harmless, specific, antigenic component to induce protective immunity against a particular infectious agent (Okumu, 2020). Vaccines are preparations that contain non-infectious fragments, weakened (attenuated), or inactivated form of bacteria or viruses that do not cause illness, or a modified, harmless toxin called a toxoid (Savoy, 2024). The body's immune system responds to the vaccine by producing antibodies that recognize and attack the specific pathogen. If the person is exposed to the same pathogen in the future, these antibodies help to prevent illness through a rapid immune response.

Beyond personal protections, immunization also benefits the entire community. A vaccinated child not only protects themselves but also protects others by preventing the spread of vaccine-preventable diseases through herd immunity. Childhood vaccinations are critical in protecting children and other vulnerable groups against serious vaccine-preventable diseases, including measles, mumps, rubella, polio, diphtheria, pertussis, and tetanus (Nandi and Shet, 2020). A child is considered fully vaccinated if they have received a Bacillus Calmette-Guérin (BCG) vaccination against tuberculosis; three doses of the vaccine to prevent diphtheria, pertussis, and tetanus (DPT); at least three doses of the polio vaccine; and one dose of the measles vaccine (Emeahara, Ozuemba, and Nnaemezie, 2021).

Immunization has contributed to Millennium Development Goal 4 to reduce childhood mortality. All-cause mortality in children younger than 5 years decreased by 47% that is 9.7 million deaths between the year 2000 and 5.2 million deaths in 2019 respectively (United Nations Interagency Group for Child Mortality Estimation, 2024). Also, immunizations have prevented over five deaths per minute and saved up to 3 million lives annually, even before the Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19), pandemic (United Nations Children's Fund (2022).

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Furthermore, available records show that about 2–3 million lives are saved every year by current immunization programs, contributing to a marked reduction in the mortality of children under five years of age globally from 93 deaths per 1,000 live births in 1990 to 39 deaths per 1,000 live births in 2018 (World Health Organization, 2020).

Every year, children under the age of five die or experience disabilities from vaccine preventable diseases such as measles, poliomyelitis, tetanus, whooping cough, tuberculosis and so on. In Nigeria, 15.5% (3 million) of the global total of 19.4 million unvaccinated infants are found, which accounted for 22% of under-five deaths and numerous cases of permanent disability (Oli, Ogwaluonye, Onubogu, Ozumba, Agbaenyi and Okeke, 2021). Reported concerns and misconceptions, about vaccine safety can impact immunization efforts, putting under five children at risk of contracting common infectious diseases. The Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19), pandemic also, has had a significant impact on routine immunization services, with disruptions in service delivery, vaccine refusal, and delays in vaccination schedules (World Health Organization, 2020).

In addition, other factors such as age and number of children could shape mothers understanding and perceptions about childhood vaccination. Studies have shown that adequate vaccination is important to reduce child mortality rates which can have significant impacts on various sectors including; economy, education, governance, security, and health-care. Primary health centers (PHCs), are the frontline health-care facilities for delivering essential maternal and child health services, including routine immunization. They play a vital role in reaching the underserved and remote populations. Evidence for this includes the number of sick children admitted in hospitals daily, as well as high rates of infant mortality

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and morbidity. Furthermore, there is lack of studies on adherence to childhood routine immunization in the area. To fully eradicate the spread of some diseases from Nkwerre Local Government Area, adherence to childhood routine immunization must be observed to keep the herd immunity against vaccine preventable diseases high. This study, therefore, aims to investigate the knowledge and attitude of pregnant women towards adherence to childhood routine immunization in primary health centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to ascertain the knowledge and attitude of pregnant women towards adherence to childhood routine immunization in primary health centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area.

Specifically, the study determined the:

1. Knowledge of pregnant women on childhood routine immunization in primary health centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area.
2. Attitude of pregnant women towards adherence to childhood routine immunization in primary health centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area.
3. Mean knowledge of pregnant women on childhood routine immunization in primary health centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area based on age.
4. Mean knowledge of pregnant women on childhood routine immunization in primary health centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area based on parity level.
5. Attitude of pregnant women towards adherence to childhood routine immunization in primary health centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area based on age.

6. Attitude of pregnant women towards adherence to childhood routine immunization in primary health centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area based on parity level.

METHODS

The study employed a descriptive survey research design. Nkwerre Local Government Area is one of the 27 local government areas in Imo State, with its administrative headquarters located in Nkwerre town. According to a verified record available the population consists of 1,449 pregnant women attending antenatal care services in Nkwerre Local Government Area. The sample size of the study consisted of 240 pregnant women attending antenatal care services at the various primary health centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area. A multi-stage sampling procedure was employed to determine the sample size. The researcher designed two instruments used for data collection viz; Knowledge Test on Childhood Routine Immunization (KTCRI) and Attitude Towards Adherence to Childhood Routine Immunization (ATACRI) questionnaires. The reliability of the instruments was determined using the Kuder-Richardson (K-R20) method for the knowledge test, which yielded a coefficient value of 0.97. Additionally, Cronbach's Alpha internal consistency measure for the attitude items yielded a coefficient value of 0.94. The research questions were answered using means and standard deviations while the null hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to determine whether there are any statistically significant differences between the means of three or more independent groups and Post hoc multiple comparison tests was used to identify which specific groups differ from each other, while controlling for Type I error (false positive), at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Research Question One.

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What is the knowledge of pregnant women on childhood routine immunization in primary health centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area?

Table 1: Mean Knowledge on Childhood Routine Immunization of Pregnant Women in Primary Health Centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area

	N	Min.	Max.	Mean	SD	Remark
Percentage scores on Knowledge of childhood routine immunization	211	17.86	100.00	68.97	26.92	Good

Table 1 shows, that the participants’ distribution of scores on the test of knowledge of childhood routine immunization ranged from 17.86 and 100.00. The mean knowledge score was 68.89. This value indicates that pregnant women in health centers in Nkwerre Local Government Area, had good knowledge of childhood routine immunization.

Research Question Two.

What is the attitude of pregnant women, towards adherence to childhood routine immunization in primary health centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area?

Table 2: Mean Attitude of Childhood Routine Immunization among Pregnant Women in Primary Health Centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area

	N	Min.	Max.	Mean	SD	Remark
Attitude to adherence to Childhood Routine Immunization	211	32.00	85.00	53.00	13.28	Negative

As shown in Table 2 pregnant women’s minimum attitude score was 32.00 while the maximum score was 85.00. The mean attitude score was 53.00. This implies that pregnant women in primary health centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area had negative attitude to childhood routine immunization.

Research Question Three.

What is the mean knowledge of pregnant women on childhood routine immunization in primary health centres in Nkwere Local Government Area based on age?

Table 3: Mean Knowledge on Childhood Routine Immunization of Pregnant Women in Primary Health Centres in Nkwere Local Government Area Based on Age Range

Age	N	Mean	SD	Remark
18-30 years	91	62.44	26.02	Good
31-40 years	84	76.02	26.52	Very good
41 years & above	36	69.05	26.64	Good

Table shows the disaggregated mean knowledge score of pregnant women based on different age groups. Those between 31-40 years of age had the highest knowledge of childhood routine immunization as shown by their mean knowledge score of 76.02. This was followed by those between 41 years and above as demonstrated by their mean knowledge score of 69.02. Pregnant women between ages of 18-30 had the lowest knowledge of childhood routine immunization.

Research Question Four.

What is the mean knowledge of pregnant women on childhood routine immunization in primary health centres in Nkwere Local Government Area based on parity level?

Table 4: Mean Knowledge on Childhood Routine Immunization of Pregnant Women in Primary Health Centres in Nkwere Local Government Area Based on Parity Level

Age	N	Mean	SD	Remark
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1 child	30	56.19	24.83	Fair
2-3 children	112	70.79	26.93	Very good
4 children & above	69	71.58	26.59	Very Good

Table 4 shows the disaggregated mean knowledge score of pregnant women of different parity levels. Pregnant women with 4 children and above had the highest mean knowledge of childhood routine immunization as shown by their mean knowledge score of 71.58. This was followed by those with 2 to 3 children with mean knowledge score of 70.79. Women with only 1 child had the least knowledge of childhood routine immunization. This suggests that the more children the women have, the more knowledge they acquired about childhood routine immunization.

Research Question Five.

What is the attitude of pregnant women towards adherence to childhood routine immunization in primary health centres in Nkwere Local Government Area based on age?

Table 5: Mean Attitude to Childhood Routine Immunization of Pregnant Women in Primary Health Centres in Nkwere Local Government Area Based on Age Range

Age	N	Mean	SD	Remark
18-30 years	91	51.49	13.85	Negative
31-40 years	84	54.55	13.15	Negative
41 years & above	36	53.22	11.99	Negative

Table 5 displays the mean attitude to childhood routine immunization based on the age of pregnant women visiting health centres in Nkwere Local Government Area. The result shows that pregnant women across all the age groups had negative attitude to childhood

routine immunization. This was demonstrated by their mean attitude scores which were 51.49 for those between 18=30 years of age; 54.55 for those between 31-40 years; and 53.22 for 41 years of and above. However, those between 31.40 had slightly better mean attitude score.

Research Question Six.

What is the attitude of pregnant women towards adherence to childhood routine immunization in primary health centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area based on parity level?

Table 6: Mean Attitude to Childhood Routine Immunization of Pregnant Women in Primary Health Centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area Based on Party Level.

Parity	N	Mean	SD
1 child	30	50.73	12.52
2-3 children	112	52.85	12.98
4 children & above	69	54.25	14.11

Table 6 displays the mean attitude of pregnant women towards childhood routine immunization. Although pregnant women of different parity levels had negative attitude, those with 4 children and above had a slightly higher mean attitude score (Mean = 54.25) than those with 2-3 children (Mean = 52.85); and 1 child (50.73) respectively.

Hypothesis One.

There is no significant difference in mean knowledge score of pregnant women towards childhood routine immunization in primary health centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area based on age.

Table 7: Analysis of Variance on Mean Knowledge on Childhood Routine Immunization by Age of Pregnant Women in Primary Health Centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area.

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F(2,208)	p	Remark
Between Groups	8054.56	2	4027.28	5.81	.004	Significant
Within Groups	144156.32	208	693.06			
Total	152210.88	210				

The result in Table 7 shows that there was a significant difference in the mean knowledge on childhood routine immunization among pregnant women in primary health centres in Nkwerre Local Government Areas based on their age range, $F(2,208) = 5.81$, $p = 0.004$. The null hypothesis was rejected since the p-value was less than 0.05 level of significant. A posthoc test was conducted to ascertain the age group that was significantly different from the others. The result as presented in Table 8, indicates that pregnant women between 31 – 40 years had significantly higher mean knowledge of childhood routine immunization than those between 18-30 years of age. However, their mean knowledge was not significantly greater than mean knowledge of those who were 41 years and above.

Table 8: Posthoc Multiple Comparison Tests Comparing Mean Knowledge on Childhood Routine Immunization among Pregnant Women of Different Age Groups.

(I) Age	(J) Age	Mean Diff. (I-J)	SE	P	Remark
18-30 years	31-40 years	-13.58	3.98	.004	Significant
	41 years & above	-6.61	5.18	.445	Not Significant
31-40 years	41 years & above	6.97269	5.24427	.415	Not Significant

Hypothesis Two.

There is no significant difference in the mean knowledge score of pregnant women towards childhood routine immunization in primary health centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area based on parity level.

Table 9: Analysis of Variance on Mean Knowledge on Childhood Routine Immunization by Parity Level of Pregnant Women in Primary Health Centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area.

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F(2,208)	p	Remark
Between Groups	5742.18	2	2871.09	4.08	.018	Significant
Within Groups	146468.70	208	704.18			
Total	152210.88	210				

The result in Table 9 shows that there was a significant difference in the mean knowledge on childhood routine immunization among pregnant women with different parity level, $F(2,208) = 4.08$, $p = 0.018$. The null hypothesis was rejected since the p-value was less than 0.05 level of significant. As displayed in posthoc multiple comparison Table 10, pregnant women with only 1 child had significantly lower knowledge of childhood routine immunization than pregnant women of other parity levels. However, those with 2 – 3 children were not significantly different from those with 4 children and above in their knowledge of childhood routine immunization.

Table 10: Posthoc Multiple Comparison Tests Comparing Mean Knowledge on Childhood Routine Immunization among Pregnant Women of Different Parity Levels.

(I) Parity	(J) Parity	Mean Diff (I-J)	SE	P	Remark
1 child	2-3 children	-14.60	5.46	.030	Significant
	4 children & above	-15.39	5.80	.031	Significant
2-3 children	4 children & above	-0.79	4.06	.981	Not significant

Hypothesis Three.

There is no significant difference in the mean knowledge score of pregnant women towards adherence to childhood routine immunization in primary health centers in Nkwerre Local Government Area based on age.

Table 11: Analysis of Variance on Mean Attitude to Childhood Routine Immunization based on Age of Pregnant Women in Primary Health Centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area.

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F(2,208)	p	Remark
Between Groups	409.22	2	204.61	1.16	.315	Not Significant
Within Groups	36639.78	208	176.15			
Total	37049.00	210				

The Analysis of Variances (ANOVA) results displayed in Table 11 shows that there was no significant difference in the mean attitude to childhood routine immunization among pregnant women of different age groups, $F(2,208) = 1.16$, $p = 0.315$, therefore, the hypothesis was not rejected since the p-value was greater than 0.05 level of significant.

Hypothesis Four.

There is no significant difference in the mean attitude score of pregnant women towards adherence to childhood routine immunization in primary health centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area based on parity level.

Table 12: Analysis of Variance on Mean Attitude to Childhood Routine Immunization by Parity Level of Pregnant Women in Primary Health Centres in Nkwerre Local Government Area

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F(2,208)	p	Remark
Between Groups	263.90	2	131.95	0.75	.475	Not Significant
Within Groups	36785.098	208	176.85			
Total	37048.995	210				

The result in Table 10 shows that there was a non- significant difference in the mean attitude to childhood routine immunization among pregnant women with different parity level, $F(2,208) = 0.75$, $p = 0.475$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was not rejected since the p-value was greater than 0.05 level of significant.

Discussion of Results.

Knowledge of pregnant women on childhood routine immunization.

The findings of the study revealed that the general knowledge of childhood routine immunization among pregnant women in Nkwerre Local Government Area is good. This suggests that an average mother in this area has basic knowledge on immunization. In a related study, Emeahara, et al., (2021), found that mothers had good knowledge of children's vaccination. In another study conducted by Olabode, (2023), mothers in Akure North Local Government Area had an overall good knowledge of immunization. Onwuchekwa, et al.

(2022), in a similar study also reported that most mothers had good knowledge of immunization. The finding is also, consistent with the study of Irodi et al. (2023), that all nursing mothers were aware of immunization services, and were aware of 4-6 types of vaccines. Some of the identified vaccines being given to children during immunization appointments include Bacillus Calmete Guerine and Oral Polio Vaccine, followed by Hepatitis B vaccine, Diphtheria, Pertusis, Tetanus vaccine and Pentavalent vaccine with most mothers stating that health workers and media are their primary sources of information on immunization (Uwaibi, et al. 2020).

Attitude of pregnant women towards adherence to childhood routine immunization.

The findings of the study showed that pregnant women in Nkwerre Local Government Area had a negative attitude towards childhood routine immunization. This finding is in contrast with other studies that reported generally positive attitudes towards immunization among mothers. For instance, Idowu, et al. (2024), reported that mothers in Alimosho Local Government Area, Lagos State, had positive attitudes towards vaccination. This was supported by another study carried out by Namutebi and Anywar (2024), that high levels of positive attitudes towards immunization were found among mothers and caregivers. Negative attitudes predispose to a poor practice towards adherence to childhood routine immunization. It has been shown in, several studies that mothers with negative attitudes tend to fear and therefore be reluctant in taking their children for routine immunization.

Conclusion.

The finding of the study on knowledge and attitude of pregnant women towards adherence to childhood routine immunization in primary health centers in Nkwerre Local Government

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Area, demonstrated that pregnant women attending antenatal care possess good knowledge of childhood routine immunization, this knowledge on childhood routine immunization was significantly influenced by age and parity level. However, despite the respondents good knowledge on immunization, it does not translate to positive attitude. The participants show a negative attitude towards adherence to childhood routine immunization. Their attitude towards adherence to childhood routine immunization was not significantly influenced by age and parity levels.

Recommendations.

The following recommendations were made based on the findings and conclusion of the study:

1. Governments at all levels and health care givers should intensify efforts to disseminate information other than traditional health educations that the mothers receive during, antenatal care and infant welfare clinic e.g. TV adverts, radio adverts, immunization flyers, use of town criers especially in the villages. This will help to sustain maternal knowledge on childhood immunization.
2. Health-care workers should engage with the community and religious leaders to identify reasons leading to poor attitudes towards immunization as well as raise awareness on the benefits of childhood immunization. These efforts will help to address any misconception, build trust and motivate the individuals to participate in such programs.

3. Nursing mothers should be encouraged to keep their children immunization cards or records safe and accurate. This will help them to know when their children are due for vaccination. Also, use of bulk SMS by the health care givers as a reminder and medium of information dissemination on childhood immunization

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